

BEHAVIOUR OF ELECTROLYTES IN MIXED SOLVENTS. PART VI.
VISCOSITY OF MAGNESIUM CHLORIDE AND POTASSIUM
SULPHATE IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES AT 35°

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The viscosities of magnesium chloride and potassium sulphate in dioxane-water mixtures at 10, 20, and 30% by weight of dioxane have been studied at 35°. The data fit well with the modified form of the Jones-Dole equation. The value of B has been found dependent on the solvent composition in case of both the electrolytes.

The modified Jones-Dole equation,

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC^r,$$

suggested by us (*Curr. Sci.*, 1956, 25, 337) has been found to apply in case of mono-monovalent electrolytes like KCl and NaCl in dioxane-water mixtures at 35° (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 56; 1959, 36, 613). With a view to verifying the applicability of the equation in case of bi-monovalent and uni-bivalent type of electrolytes, the viscosities of $MgCl_2$ and K_2SO_4 in 10, 20, and 30% dioxane-water mixtures by weight have been determined at 35°.

EXPERIMENTAL

$MgCl_2$ and K_2SO_4 used were of B.D.H. AnalaR quality. The estimation of Mg^{2+} and Cl^- content and the recrystallisation of K_2SO_4 have been described previously (*loc. cit.*). The preparation of the solvents, solutions and measurements of viscosity and conductance were the same as reported earlier (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE I

Solvent composition.	$MgCl_2$			K_2SO_4		
	$A \times 10^2$.	B .	r .	$A \times 10^2$.	B .	r .
10	1.640	0.43	1.00	1.300	0.28	1.00
20	1.830	0.54	0.95	1.500	0.30	0.99
30	2.055	0.84	1.05	2.600	0.38	0.94

TABLE II

Salts.	Conc. (moles/litre)	Observed viscosity.	Calc. viscosity by	
			J. D.	Modified J.D.
$MgCl_2$	0.100	1.0662	1.0598	1.0664
	0.001	1.0014	1.0011	1.0014
K_2SO_4	0.100	1.0354	1.0347	1.0353
	0.001	1.0008	1.0008	1.0008

DISCUSSION

The change in viscosity with concentration for aqueous solution of electrolytes is satisfactorily represented by the Jones-Dole equation (*loc. cit.*). The evaluation of the equivalent conductance (Λ_0) at zero concentration and the calculation of 'A' by the Falkenhagen and Vernon expression have been reported earlier (*loc. cit.*). The usual procedure to test the Jones-Dole equation has been applied, and it has been found that the equation holds good only for 10% dioxane solvent composition. For 20% and 30% solvent composition, the Jones-Dole equation is, however, inadequate, and its modified form represents the experimental results satisfactorily.

The values of A , B and, x for different solvent compositions can be calculated as described previously. These values for solutions of $MgCl_2$ and K_2SO_4 at different solvent compositions are recorded in Table I. The relative viscosities were next calculated by the use of these determined values of B and x . Calculated and observed values are in good agreement for the range of concentrations of the solute 0.100M to 0.001M investigated at 10, 20, and 30% dioxane composition. Only two data for each of the electrolytes at 20% solvent composition have been recorded in Table II for illustration.

The data recorded in Table I show that with increase of the dioxane content in the solvent the value of B also increases, indicating its dependence on the composition of the solvent.

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